

Original papers

Long-Term Field Experiments Overview Map: An interactive open-access metadata platform to enhance networking and data reuse

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural long-term experiments (LTEs) are infrastructures for understanding the long-term impacts of agricultural practices on soil health, crop productivity, and environmental sustainability. Some spanning over 150 years, they generate essential data on crops, fertilization, tillage, irrigation, and land management. However, the fragmented landscape of LTEs leading to data accessibility challenges have limited their full research potential.

We introduce an overview map for LTEs (LTE-Map) (<https://lte.bonares.de>), an open-access and interactive platform that centralizes and provide valuable information (metadata) from LTEs. Developed with LTE institutions and data users, its structured model standardizes experimental and organizational data for global interoperability. It enables researchers to efficiently access LTE metadata, aligning with FAIR principles, and serves as a user-friendly gateway to key experimental and environmental information.

Currently, the LTE-Map documents 688 trials globally including the earliest experiment established in 1843. While most sites are in Europe (621), more than 60 are located outside, underlining the potential for global expansion. The map shows that LTEs are predominantly focused on arable land and crop rotation studies.

The LTE-Map provides a flexible framework for exploring trials, supporting both data providers and researchers based on relevant criteria. It stands as a cornerstone of data management, fosters collaboration and reuse, and has already enabled multiple studies, demonstrating its value as proof of concept for advancing experimental research.

1. Introduction

Long-term field experiments (LTEs) have been the cornerstone of agricultural research for decades, providing critical insights into how different cropping practices impact soil health, crop productivity, and environmental sustainability over extended periods (Körschens, 2006). LTEs enable researchers to monitor long-term trends and identify sustainable practices by studying the individual and combined effects of crop rotations, tillage systems, fertilization methods, and irrigation practices (Gocke et al., 2023). By spanning decades or even more than one century, LTEs offer invaluable data that helps inform evidence-based agricultural policy and sustainable land and crop management practices in the long-term (Stützel et al., 2016; Watson et al., 2024). The evolution of soil attributes with respect to agricultural practices used is

often slow and the effect of a particular practice can take years or decades before showing a visible effect on the soil. For instance, changes in soil organic carbon are usually observed over several years. Similarly, substantial improvements in soil structure, for instance, by no- or reduced tillage, can only be observed after several years. In this respect, LTEs are essential in order to assess the long-term effect of a management practice beyond the agronomical season or the typical crop rotation.

Here, LTE is defined as an agricultural experiment lasting at least 20 years, capturing dynamics such as soil organic carbon changes, crop rotations, and pest management effects and has a static design (Grosse et al., 2021). The EJP SOIL initiative also uses the same definition for LTE but complements them with defining Mid-Term Experiments (MTEs) as experiments lasting a minimum of five years with

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standardized controlled treatments (Blanchy et al., 2024). Both MTEs and LTEs have been added to this LTE-Map. Regardless of the definition, under changing climatic conditions, LTE data is indispensable for researchers, decision-makers, and environmental organizations to develop strategies that mitigate climate-related risks to agricultural productivity (Donmez et al., 2022a).

Despite the immense value of LTE data, its full potential remains untapped due to significant limitations in how it is managed and shared. LTE datasets are scattered across institutions, stored in diverse formats, and lacking standardized descriptions and metadata. This data disharmonization makes data from LTE difficult to find, access, reuse, analyze, and synthesize.

Over the years, multiple national, international, and global LTE networks have been established to harmonize and standardize LTE experiments and data, including GLTEN (Global Long-Term Experiment Network, UK), IOSDV (International Organic Nitrogen Fertilization Experiments), NLFT (National Long-Term Fertilization Trials, HU), RetiBio II (ITA), and research projects such as BonaRes (“Soil as a sustainable resource for the bioeconomy”, DE) and EJP SOIL (EU) (Donmez et al., 2022b). However, each initiative follows its own data standards, further complicating interoperability and data exchange. The lack of centralized, structured, and accessible LTE repositories prevents large-scale *meta*-analyses and cross-experiment comparisons, essential for addressing global agricultural challenges. For instance, finding LTE data for specific research needs, such as yield comparisons or soil organic carbon studies, remains challenging due to those problems (Caldron et al., 2024).

Since the 1980 s, there has been growing interest in developing LTE data infrastructures and research networks through literature synthesis and multi-institutional collaborations (Bybee-Finley et al., 2024). Notable initiatives include EuroSOMNET, a database on soil organic matter LTEs across Europe, storing more than 25 experiments (Smith et al., 2002). NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network, USA) and LTAR (Long-Term Agroecosystem Research Network, USDA), providing cross-site LTE data syntheses (Kleinman et al., 2018; Dantzer et al., 2023). IOSDV is an international collaborative research initiative investigating the long-term effects of mineral and organic nitrogen fertilization on soil health, crop yields, initiated in 1983. It comprises a network of LTEs across multiple countries (e.g. Germany, Hungary, Slovenia, and Estonia) (Spiegel et al., 2010; Csitári et al., 2021; Stumpf et al., 2021) and provides standardized setups for nitrogen applications. DRIVES Project, compiling 495 site-years of data from 21 LTEs in the US to study agricultural multifunctionality (Bybee-Finley et al., 2024). The EJP SOIL research program (<https://ejpsoil.eu/>) curated an open-source collection of metadata records of European LTEs (Blanchy et al., 2024).

These initiatives provide a certain visibility and access to LTE metadata. However, the findability and accessibility of most LTE metadata and data remain difficult and are often distributed across scientific papers, reports, web links and institution-specific databases. To fully leverage LTE datasets, adherence to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles is critical and many data platforms lack the technical infrastructure for true FAIR compliance, limiting data integration, harmonization, and accessibility. A centralized, interactive, and standardized platform that facilitates data harmonization, networking, and open-access provisioning would be a major asset to the LTE research community.

Many platforms focus on specific practices (e.g., fertilization, soil organic matter) or are limited to particular geographic regions. In addition, heterogeneous metadata structures hinder interoperability and complicate cross-site integration. Another challenge is the lack of a long-term, permanent tool that ensures continuity of access and sustainable maintenance of LTE metadata beyond the lifetime of individual projects (e.g., BonaRes, EJP SOIL). Consequently, researchers aiming to conduct large-scale syntheses or cross-country comparisons continue to face barriers in locating, accessing, and reusing LTE data. These limitations underscore the need for a complementary, global, and interactive

platform that provides standardized, FAIR-aligned, and permanent entry points to LTE metadata, thereby enhancing the research potential of LTEs.

To address these challenges, this paper aims to introduce an agricultural Long-Term Field Experiments Overview Map (LTE-Map) (<https://lte.bonares.de>), an open-access platform designed to centralize and enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and reuse of LTE metadata and data outputs. It addresses these gaps by combining a harmonized metadata standard with an interactive geospatial interface that ensures interoperability and user-friendly exploration, while explicitly implementing FAIR principles at a global scale to provide a novel and sustainable tool for long-term agricultural research. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to (i) identify and document LTEs in the global extent using a standardized metadata model; (ii) develop an interactive map that enables researchers and practitioners to efficiently explore LTEs according to specific management practices as a gateway for data-driven LTE research; (iii) align LTE metadata with FAIR principles to improve data reuse and interoperability. The study examines how our LTE-Map complements existing infrastructures such as the BonaRes Repository (Lachmuth et al., 2025) an open research data infrastructure for the publication of soil and agricultural data developed within the BonaRes initiative (<https://www.bonares.de>), by consolidating and standardizing metadata from LTEs worldwide. It explores the role of the LTE-Map as an entry point to LTE experimental data recently published in the BonaRes Repository, offering researchers, practitioners, and policymakers access to decades of experimental (meta)data. We evaluate how a harmonized and interactive metadata platform can support cross-experiment syntheses, regional assessments, and simulation modeling on climate change impacts, thereby contributing to long-term agricultural research. This initiative not only democratizes access to valuable LTE data but also encourages new analyses, networking, and cross-regional studies that were previously constrained by fragmented data systems. In doing so, the LTE-Map contributes to advancing agricultural sustainability and provides a valuable resource for researchers and policymakers seeking to understand the long-term effects of agricultural practices, also under changing climatic conditions. In addition to its agricultural relevance, LTE-Map contributes to the computing and data infrastructure dimension of digital agriculture. It applies open data standards and a FAIR-compliant metadata model to ensure interoperability, while its interactive geospatial interface supports decision-making, data integration, and cross-site comparability.

2. Systematic collection and organization of LTE metadata

The LTE-Map comprises global LTE metadata from different sources within a comprehensive bibliographic review, personal communication with numerous LTE holders, and data harvesting with external initiatives through agreement. For the literature review, the metadata searches (last update in November 2024) have been conducted from scientific journals, books, research notes and websites addressing the research themes and parameters of the agricultural LTEs. It included a systematic search in the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection (<https://apps.webofknowledge.com/>) and SCOPUS (<https://www.scopus.com/>) as well as the Google Scholar databases to find relevant material for available LTE information. This search was based on the English and German keywords.

- “long-term field experiment”
- “long-term experiment”
- “long-term field trial”, and
- “long-term trial”,
- “Dauerfeldversuch”,
- “Dauerdüngungsversuch”,
- “Dauerversuch”,
- “Langzeitfeldversuch” and
- “Langzeitversuch”

Initially, the search was focused on Germany (nationally funded metadata base) (Grosse et al., 2021). With a growing interest from the soil-agricultural research community, the search has since expanded its scope to an international level.

Publications, providing LTE-specific information (e.g., site location, duration, land use, and farming categories), were selected and processed, and the extracted information was organized into a metadata table covering site details and experimental setup. Search keywords (both English and German) were reviewed to be compatible with the thesaurus AGROVOC (FAO – <https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>), providing a standardized terminology for findability/discoverability across indexed literature. Metadata collection was initiated in Germany, and, after LTE data from neighboring countries was increasingly provided, extended to Europe and the global level.

In addition to the bibliographic review, a significant number of LTE metadata recorded on the LTE-Map were received by personal communication. After setting up direct contact with the LTE owner, LTE meta-information was collected through the BonaRes Fact Sheet (Grosse et al., 2019). The fact sheets are based on the information that is relevant for the community in order to make a selection based on the relevant research questions and to enable contact to be made with the LTE operators. The development of the search and collaboration procedure of the LTE-Map is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The initial unpublished questionnaire for an LTE operator included standardized LTE side information (e.g., relief information, soil profile

description, and land use) to transfer relevant information into an LTE database and an overview map (the LTE-Map for Germany). Empty fact sheets were forwarded to LTE holders, and filled returns were reviewed by data stewards. Due to user requirements, meta-information fields have been expanded several times, and, as part of the increased international focus of BonaRes and increasing enquiries from abroad, the sheet has been published in a bilingual (EN/DE) version (Grosse et al., 2019).

As a next step, more LTE metadata were collected through agreement and/or communication with significant international initiatives (EU-funded projects, agricultural data networks). To facilitate the networking phase, we organized an international LTE workshop with 45 registered participants from the LTE community in 2022 (Donmez et al., 2023a). Furthermore, a significant step included a Memorandum of Understanding between the National Research project BonaRes and the European Research project EJP SOIL for LTE data provision and exchange, where LTE-Map was positioned to host EJP SOIL 7.3 LTE meta-database (Blanchy et al., 2022). To initiate this exchange, the EJP SOIL metadata template (Blanchy et al., 2024) was adapted to the existing BonaRes template, supporting LTE-specific fields (Donmez et al., 2022a). The EJP SOIL LTE metadatabase was then further processed and merged with BonaRes metadata records on the LTE-Map.

Fig. 1. Development of the search and networking procedure of the LTE-Map.

3. Technical infrastructure of the LTE-Map

As a product of the BonaRes Project (<https://www.bonares.de>), the LTE-Map has been systematically developed through a structured, two-phase process to ensure comprehensive documentation, accessibility, and interoperability of LTEs. The development included an integrated

approach for creating a robust platform i.e. (1) establishment of a standardized metadata model based on the BonaRes metadata schema and, (2) implementation of an interactive, user-friendly digital platform for visualization and data reuse. The development of LTE-Map is continuously maintained to address the dynamic nature of LTE data management and evolving user needs, with regular version updates

Fig. 2. Unified Modeling Language (UML)-based overview of the LTE-Map metadata model (Namespace prefixes indicate the originating metadata schema (ims: INSPIRE, dc: DataCite, br: BonaRes). Multiplicities specify whether metadata elements are mandatory (1..1), optional (0..1), or repeatable (0..*)).

available directly on the platform.

3.1. Metadata model/structure

The metadata model of the LTE-Map was developed based on the BonaRes Metadata Schema (Specka et al., 2019), with elements from DataCite 4.4. Together, the metadata categories defined for the LTE-Map comprise a cohesive system that supports data reuse with metadata as a basis for further research, accessibility, and interoperability with broader spatial and research infrastructure initiatives in the LTE context. The information is grouped in a metadata table in different fields (e.g., site information, experimental setup, soil information, trial categorization and organization), mainly based on the BonaRes Fact Sheet (Grosse et al., 2019). As illustrated in Fig. 2, the metadata model is formalized as a Unified Modeling Language (UML) class diagram with *lte_experiment* (*experiment_id*, *experiment_name*) at its core. We aim to publish the LTE metadata schema under an open license, ensuring that it complies with FAIR principles and remains accessible to the research community, in alignment with semantic artefacts described, for example, by Amdouni and Jonquet (2022) and Soares et al. (2024).

The central class contains the unique experiment identifier and name, and connects to several metadata categories. Administrative information (*administrative_information*) records institutional and organizational attributes (*index_ID*, *trial_institution*, *land_use_type*, *research_themes*). Spatial descriptors (*spatial_information*) define *site_name*, *country*, *continent*, and *coordinates*, while temporal information (*temporal_information*) specifies *start_date*, *trial_duration*, and *trial_status*. The experimental design is represented through *experimental_setup* (*number_of_levels*, *one_factorial_lte*, *two_factorial_lte*, *multifactorial_lte*, *randomization*, *replication*, *number_of_plots*, *plot_size*) and complemented by *field_management* (*position_of_exactness*, *field_size*). Soil properties are documented under *soil_information* (*soil_group_wrb*, *texture_class*, *sand_pct*, *silt_pct*, *clay_pct*, *bulk_density*, *organic_matter*, *further_soil_information*).

Beyond experiment-specific metadata, the model includes external relationships. Each LTE is linked to one or more hosting organization, with attributes such as literature references, sources, networks, AGROVOC-controlled keywords, and contact information. Furthermore, experiments can be associated with one or more *research_theme* entries, explicitly marked as controlled terms sourced from FAO AGROVOC. Multiplicity indicators specify whether components are mandatory (1..1), optional (0..1), or repeatable (0..*), thereby ensuring both flexibility and formal rigor in metadata representation. It enabled us to represent research themes as controlled terms linked directly to experiments, rather than as free-text attributes, thereby ensuring semantic consistency and interoperability across recorded LTEs.

In addition to these structural elements, a key step was the harmonization of metadata collected by different initiatives. The LTE-Map metadata do not represent a classical metadata schemes used in research data management (e.g., DataCite or INSPIRE), but rather trial-level information relevant to agricultural and soil research (e.g., *trial_categorization*, *experimental_setup*, *soil_information*). These descriptors were originally collected in different formats by the BonaRes and EJP SOIL initiatives, whose templates did not match one-to-one. A harmonization process was therefore required in which fields were mapped (e.g., BonaRes *trial_categorization* to EJP *experiment_type*), adapted (i.e., *experimental_setup*) newly created where necessary. Many attributes were directly mappable (e.g., *country*, *site_name*, *trial_institution*), while others required adjustments such as merging latitude and longitude into a single coordinate field. Some attributes were unique to BonaRes (e.g., *texture_class*, *bulk_density*, *organic_matter*) and were retained as optional fields, whereas a few descriptors were specific to EJP SOIL (e.g., *further_soil_information*) and were included as Supplementary attributes. This harmonization resulted in a unified schema that ensures interoperability while preserving the richness and specificity of agricultural LTEs. Selected representative field mappings between BonaRes and EJP SOIL are provided in Appendix 1.

Building on this harmonized schema, the LTE-Map structures meta-data into several complementary dimensions (e.g., *organization*, *administrative_information*, *spatial_information*, *temporal_information*, *trial_categorization*, *experimental_setup*, *field_management*, *soil_information*, *research_theme*). Rather than functioning as isolated descriptors, these categories together provide the methodological transparency and contextual detail needed for cross-site comparability, spatial analysis, and integration with broader research infrastructures.

The field *soil_information* was prioritized to capture slowly evolving properties central to LTEs. Their descriptors enable linkages with soil monitoring networks and allow for sustainability assessments across sites. In our LTE-Map, soil attributes are captured as contextual metadata at the trial level and are not intended to represent long-term soil monitoring. Temporal changes in soil properties are instead documented within the underlying experimental datasets, which can be discovered through the LTE-Map and accessed via links to external repositories (primarily the BonaRes Repository – <https://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMVY>). *trial_categorization* reduces heterogeneity by using Boolean flags (*tillage_trial*, *fertilization_trial*, *crop_rotation_trial*) complemented by broader descriptors (*trial_category*, *holder_category*, *other_practice_or_system*). This structure facilitates meta-analyses and comparative studies while allowing flexibility for less common systems categorized as “other.” *experimental_setup* metadata document factorial structure, all essential for assessing methodological comparability. Closely linked, *field_management* attributes anchor LTEs in their spatial context and enable integration with ancillary geospatial layers such as climate or vegetation data.

The field *spatial_information* allows that all LTEs can be uniquely identified and filtered across space and time. Persistent unique identifiers such as *index_ID* (*administrative_information*) and *site_name*, together with *country*, *continent*, and *coordinates* situate trials geographically, while *start_date*, *trial_duration*, and *trial_status* (*temporal_information*) document continuity and allow researchers to target LTEs active under specific conditions or timescales.

Finally, the field *organization* provides the contextual and bibliographic framework that supports provenance, attribution, and alignment with established metadata standards (e.g., DataCite, INSPIRE, Dublin Core). Attributes (*literature*, *sources*, *network*, *agrovoc_keywords*) support that all LTE metadata can be traced back to its origin, while AGROVOC-controlled keywords (AGROVOC, 2025) enhance semantic discovery. *Contact* attributes (*contact_name*, *contact_email*) are included to enable direct communication with trial holders. However, these personal data are treated as sensitive information under GDPR (EU 2016/679) and are only made available with the explicit consent of LTE owners. Where such details cannot be shared in every case, institutional affiliations are promoted as a reliable access point for users. In this context, the LTE-Map’ metadata are not only structured and reusable but also ethically managed in line with international standards.

3.2. Architecture of the LTE-Map

The LTE-Map (Fig. 3) is developed in Python 3, using Django 3.1 for backend functionality and Bootstrap 4 for a responsive user interface. It features an interactive map based on Leaflet, enabling dynamic visualization of LTE sites. The backend of the LTE-Map is currently built on a relational PostgreSQL database for metadata management. The main features of the map include search functions, an interactive interface, metadata download options (available in CSV format), word cloud, statistics tools, and pop-up menus for metadata provision.

In its standard setting, the LTE-Map also features the logos of contributing initiatives that provide metadata to the map, such as the EJP SOIL Program. These logos help highlight the collaborative nature of the dataset behind the map and its integration with broader research efforts. Additionally, the map is linked to various base map galleries, offering users multiple visualization options for the background maps. These base maps, sourced from OpenStreetMap (OSM, 2024) the Leaflet

Fig. 3. Structure and user interface of the LTE-Map (<https://lte.bonares.de>).

package, enhance the interpretability of spatial data by allowing users to toggle between different views, such as satellite imagery, terrain maps, and street maps, depending on their analytical needs.

3.3. Features of the LTE-Map supporting (meta)data discovery and reuse

The LTE-Map translates the metadata model into an interactive research infrastructure that enables transparent discovery and reuse. The extended search functioning integrates Leaflet-based geospatial visualization with faceted queries implemented through Django filters based on metadata categories. Once a search query is executed, the results are displayed both as a downloadable list and in their geographic distribution on the map (Fig. 4). Each item in the list includes a link to the respective LTE, providing access to further metadata details.

As an example of its functionality, the facet filter options on the LTE-Map utilize standardized AGROVOC terms to enable targeted searches. For instance, a test query using the keywords “fertilization” and “crop rotation” returned 365 experiments, demonstrating how the platform supports efficient discovery of LTEs by research theme. All filter terms are aligned with AGROVOC-controlled vocabularies, providing semantic consistency across heterogeneous datasets.

To further improve the discoverability of metadata and user interaction, the LTE-Map includes a Word Cloud tool that dynamically generates a visual representation of the most common keywords in the metadatabase representing various LTE management practices and studied parameters. It offers users an improved filtering on relevant LTE terms to refine their search, narrowing down LTEs that match the respective research interests. In total, approximately 50 unique keywords were included on the map. Among them, fertilization appears as the most prominent keyword, indicating high search interest in fertilization-related LTEs. Soil and yield are among the common terms, highlighting the importance of available soil data in a meta-database.

The LTE-Map provides structured access to trial-level metadata through enriched menus that consolidate information across categories.

These menus are generated directly from the PostgreSQL database schema, consolidate trial-level descriptors defined in the LTE metadata model. They include main categories with general information, LTE extent, distribution, location, and AGROVOC thesaurus representing organizational, scientific, and management-related information aligned with the BonaRes Metadata Schema (Fig. 5).

General Information tab primarily provides descriptive details for each LTE, linking to key site and soil information categorized within the main LTE metadata model. Where available, it also provide access to research datasets via DOIs. Furthermore, the *Research Information* tab presents details on land use types and primary research themes, such as fertilizer applications. If any information is missing in these sections, the corresponding field is marked as “Unknown.”.

The *Distribution* section is closely integrated with organizational data from the metadata model, providing details on responsible institutions and related publications for each LTE. If permitted by LTE owners, this section may also include sensitive data. Additionally, the *Location* section features a direct link to the precise geographic position of each LTE on the map, enhancing spatial accessibility. The metadata recorded in these sections for each LTE is publicly available and can be exported as a PDF for easy download and user documentation.

To support comprehensive analysis, the Statistics Center function provides dynamic outputs, allowing users to explore available LTE metadata through country-based visualizations. It generates statistical summaries through various plots, offering insights into regional LTE distributions and metadata availability, enhancing data interpretation and comparative analysis within the global LTE network (Fig. 6).

The trial status plot categorizes LTEs as ongoing or finished, indicating that the majority of recorded LTEs are still active ($n = 11$) in the US, while a smaller proportion have been completed in different years. The majority of LTE in the UK indicates long-term agricultural research efforts between 20 and 50 years ($n = 6$). Arable land ($n = 227$) is the common management practice for LTEs in Germany, followed by the grassland category ($n = 37$).

Fig. 4. A search query example for the Sweden LTEs case. The list on the left displays the LTEs found in the search, while their geographic distribution is to the right reflecting the state of the LTE-Map as of April 2025 (Specific query resulted in 59 with experiments).

4. Results

4.1. LTE metadata coverage

The number of LTE in the LTE-Map has increased continuously since 2019. We have been presenting LTE-Map at numerous major international conferences (e.g., Rothamsted LTE Conference, the European Geosciences Union General Assembly, the Carbon Farming Summit, EUROSOIL, and the International Union of Soil Sciences Congresses for several years. We continue to conduct literature research, and continuously invite potential LTE holders to provide their data. In this context, a significant number of LTEs have been added between January 2024 and March 2025 (n = 67) to the LTE-Map. In March 2025, the LTE-Map includes LTE metadata from 6 continents and 42 countries. This information is structured in different data types and categories according to the metadata model developed under the BonaRes Metadata Schema. Country (a) and continent (b) based distribution of LTEs and their land use (c) in the LTE-Map is illustrated in Fig. 7 (a, b, c). The structure of the entire metadata table provided by the map is given in Appendix 2.

Based on the LTE-Map, LTEs are distributed across the globe, with a

significant clustering in Europe. The recorded metadataset indicates that Europe hosts the majority of LTEs (627 sites), and demonstrates clustering in countries such as Germany, Sweden, and Austria, which have well-established research institutions and a history of investment in long-term agricultural studies. However, this may also reflect differences in data collection efforts, for instance, Germany included a more intensive search focus in this process. Continent-based information on the recorded LTEs and main categories in the LTE-Map is provided in Table 1 and Fig. 8.

LTE metadata acquisition initially focused on the European continent. However, as the platform attracted LTE providers from outside Europe, we began integrating (meta)data on a global scale (without the intention of complete global coverage). Today, Asia and Africa host 24 and 20 LTEs, respectively, reflecting relatively limited long-term agricultural research infrastructure. North America has a moderate presence, with 13 LTEs in our records. Australia and South America, with only two LTEs each, exhibit minimal representation in our map. This distribution consists of our current records, which are promising and expected to improve with ongoing data curation efforts. The spatial distribution of LTEs in our meta-database by country is given in Fig. 9.

Detailed Metadata of LTE "Box Plot Experiment in Grossbeeren"

📍 📄 🗑️

General
LTE Extent
Distribution
Location
Agrovoc Thesaurus

LTE Description ▼

LTE Name	Box Plot Experiment in Grossbeeren	
Location	Grossbeeren	
Country	Germany	
LTE Start Date	1972	
Status	Finished	
Project Duration	50	
LTE Institution	Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops	
Institution Category	Non-university scientific institution	
DOI	https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-fd75-nca9	

Research Information ▼

Land Use Type	Arable land	
Research Theme	Effect of different mineral and organic fertilization strategies within an irrigated vegetable crop rotation system for three different soils	
LTE Category	Fertilization	
Farming Category	Conventional	

Research Parameters ▼

Research Parameter (Plant)	yield, N, P, K, Mg	
Research Parameter (Soil)	Corg, Nt, P, K, Mg, pH value	
Factor:		
Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
SoilSoil type (weak loamy sand, heavy sandy loam, medium clayey silt)	Organic fertilizer (control, farmyard manure, pine bark, harvest residues, farmyard manure + harvest residues, pine bark + harvest residues, manure solids)	Mineral fertilizer (low N-level, medium N-level, high N-level with dosage differences from 1972 to 1986 and 1986 to 2022)

Soil Information ▼

Soil Type	Arenic Luvisol (weak loamy sand), Gleyic Fluvisol (heavy sandy loam) and Luvisol-Phaeozem (medium clayey silt) according to the World Reference Base – WRB (and the Bodenkundliche Kartieranleitung – KA6)
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Crop Rotation Information ▼

Crop Rotation	10 rotations of vegetable species white cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i> L. var. capitata f. alba), carrot (<i>Daucus carota</i> L.), cucumber (<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.), leek (<i>Allium porrum</i> L.) and celery (<i>Apium graveolens</i> L. var. rapaceum Mill.)
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Fig. 5. Overview of the enriched metadata sheet and categorization of the LTE *Grossbeeren*, Germany provided in the LTE-Map.

Fig. 6. Plotted meta information for different LTE categories for the UK, US, and Germany test searches (as of March 2025).

In terms of their status, the majority of LTEs (541 trials) on the map are ongoing, indicating continuous funding and research interest, while 110 were finished, providing historical information on agricultural trends. In terms of land use, LTEs overwhelmingly target arable land (567 trials), reflecting a strong emphasis on crop production, and rotation studying various crops. Grassland LTEs (51 trials) are significantly fewer and mainly explore pasture management. Agroforestry experiments remain underrepresented (8 trials) in our records, despite its growing relevance in sustainable land-use strategies. Regarding farming systems, most LTEs focus on conventional farming (359 trials), while organic farming includes 33 trials.

In the LTE-Map, among the collected LTE data, 61 LTEs have an assigned DOI, directing users to respective LTE research data as provided in data repositories (e.g. in the BonaRes Repository). Additionally, 152 LTEs recorded in the network were documented through personal communication, either via email or the BonaRes Factsheet.

4.2. Discussion on data reuse cases, distinctive functions and the governance model of the LTE-Map

The compilation of a collection of extremely valuable LTE (meta) data with a very high coverage rate, at least for Central Europe, has been proven as an excellent starting point for agricultural scientists and modelers to browse agricultural data for individual applications. The metadata provided by the LTE-Map has facilitated numerous successful data reuse cases as a proof of concept, demonstrating both the value of LTEs and the effectiveness of the map in supporting LTE research and collaboration.

During the early development phases of our LTE network, several data collection and analysis studies were conducted. Notably, Grosse et al., (2020) performed a collective analysis of German LTEs, focusing on their classification and spatial distribution. Their findings underscored the high potential of LTE (meta)data for spatially differentiated analyses and modeling while also highlighting challenges in accessing these valuable datasets due to their dispersed nature.

To address these accessibility issues, an extensive database comprising metadata from LTEs was created (Donmez et al., 2022a; Donmez et al., 2022b). This effort significantly expanded the collection of individual metadata, further strengthened by a recent agreement between BonaRes and EJP SOIL, resulting in the most comprehensive LTE metadata set in Europe. The aggregated dataset was hosted and promoted through the LTE-Map, enhancing its role as a key resource for

decision-makers, scientists, and the public. This collaboration led to several important reuse cases, such as providing detailed metadata from mid- and long-term LTEs across Europe (Blanchy et al., 2022). By making this data accessible, the map enabled users to explore specific agricultural practices and environmental conditions, ultimately supporting a research study analyzing LTEs across diverse pedo-climatic zones (Blanchy et al., 2024).

Beyond metadata collection, the LTE-Map has supported in-depth research applications by lowering barriers to accessing dispersed LTE information by standardizing metadata, embedding it in a geospatial framework, and linking it with complementary repositories. These mechanisms enable researchers to identify suitable study sites, integrate multi-source LTE datasets, and conduct spatially explicit analyses that were previously difficult to achieve without an overarching overview. One significant reuse case involved a comprehensive modeling study (Donmez et al., 2024). This study examined net primary productivity (NPP) changes across 271 LTE sites in Germany, leveraging metadata from the LTE-Map. Additionally, LTE research data from the BonaRes Repository, serving as the primary data platform, were utilized for model validation and calibration. In this case study, for instance, the LTE-Map provided an overview of the LTE landscape and their geographic distribution, enabling the selection of a representative set of experiments spanning diverse land uses (arable, grassland, and agroforestry) and management categories for modelling. Its harmonized metadata structure was directly used as input to parameterize the biogeochemical model used in the study. Then the LTE-Map served as a gateway to the BonaRes Repository, where available LTE datasets were accessed for model validation against field measurements and eddy-covariance flux data. This integration allowed for robust cross-site calibration and validation, capturing spatial variability in ecosystem indicators (i.e., NPP) by facilitating discovering, accessing, and reusing dispersed LTE data. It substantially accelerated the workflow transforming what would have been a time-consuming data compilation process into a streamlined pipeline for large-scale biogeochemical modeling. This demonstrated the complementary efficiency of both the repository and the map in facilitating LTE data access.

Another study by Donmez et al., (2023b) focused on quantifying expected, spatially differentiated changes in agroclimatic conditions for German LTE sites, an essential step for modeling and interpreting LTE data. Using 247 LTE sites identified through the LTE-Map, the study developed a framework that integrated spatially distributed climate data and LTE metadata. This framework assessed potential climatic changes

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 7. Country (a) and continent (b) based distribution of LTEs and their land use and type of agriculture (c) in the LTE-Map reflecting the state of the LTE-Map as of April 2025.

Table 1
Continent-based information of LTEs and main categories in the LTE-Map.

Categories	Data	Description
Continent	Europe (627), Asia (24), Africa (20), North America (13), Australia (2), South America (2)	Metadata from six continents included, predominantly Europe
Countries	Germany (278), Sweden (57), Hungary (52), Great Britain (27), Austria (25), Poland (24), Italy (18), China (17), Spain (14), Denmark (14), France (14), United States of America (13)	Metadata of LTEs from 42 countries documented
Time-span	1843–2025	Time-span started with the oldest LTE from Broadbalk Experiment, UK
Duration	5–182 years	182 years time-span covered
Status	Ongoing (541), Finished (110), Unknown (33)	Most of the recorded LTEs are in ongoing status
Landuse types	Arable land (567), Grassland (51), Agroforestry (8), Pasture (14)	LTE landuse types are predominantly arable land
Farming categories	Conventional (359), Organic (33), Mixed (18), Conservation (2)	Conventional farming dominates, highlighting that traditional, high-input farming remains a research priority in LTEs

at LTE sites with experiments running for 20 years or more, based on the IPCC’s Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP). Additionally, in terms of climate change related applications, a 30-year period of a multi-factorial LTE at Martonvásár (Hungary) has been examined for traces of climate change and favorable combinations of agro-management factors (Pokovai et al., 2025). The metadata provided through the map enabled a comprehensive LTE risk assessment by analyzing variations in climate variables and agroclimatic indicators between baseline and future scenarios.

Beyond individual reuse studies, the LTE-Map holds significant

potential for data exchange and integration with other national and international LTE-focused networks. For instance, the *Diverse Rotations Improve Valuable Ecosystem Services (DRIVES)* network compiles and synthesizes LTE data to examine how crop rotation diversity influences agroecosystem multifunctionality (Bybee-Finley et al., 2024). By incorporating data from 21 North American LTEs, the DRIVES project facilitates large-scale assessments of rotational diversity’s effects on crop yield resilience, soil health, and economic performance under varying environmental conditions.

Similarly, the *LTEP-BIOCHAR* initiative focuses on the agronomic and environmental impacts of biochar, providing a community-driven platform for networking, data sharing, and methodological standardization of long-term biochar experiments (Marazza et al., 2022). Additionally, the *Global Long-Term Agricultural Experiment Network (GLTEN)* plays a crucial role in connecting and harmonizing data from LTEs worldwide, with an emphasis on soil health, crop productivity, and sustainable land management (GLTEN, 2024).

These initiatives have laid the groundwork for documenting and connecting LTEs. For instance, the EJP SOIL programme (Task 7.3), produced a comprehensive European LTE metadataset, collecting metadata through a standardized Excel template developed from earlier projects (i.e., Sandén et al., 2018). GLTEN, in turn, established a global catalogue that links LTE holders and promotes international collaboration. Our LTE-Map builds upon them by offering a platform where such outputs can be permanently hosted, further curated, and explored through additional functionalities. It extends this foundation by embedding LTE metadata within a specific, mandatory database schema designed for LTEs (Kühnert et al., 2024). Data quality is assured by rules and constraints that enforce consistency and validity in entries, with additional curation provided by data stewards. The map situates these standardized records in an interactive environment that supports scientific exploration in which users can localize LTEs on a global scale, refine discovery through advanced search and filtering tools, and access dynamic visualizations such as the statistics centre and keyword-based

Fig. 8. Evolution of research theme as a stacked area chart for land use (a) and farming categories (b) (as of April 2025).

Fig. 9. Spatial distribution of LTEs in our *meta*-database by location (as of April 2025).

word cloud. Metadata can be exported in standardized formats (PDF, CSV), enabling quick evaluation of sites and integration into modeling or synthesis studies. While GLTEN also provides a geographic overview, LTE-Map advances this function by combining geospatial representation with quality-assured metadata and interactive tools for analysis.

Moreover,

The LTE-Map is embedded in the BonaRes Repository, hosted by the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) (Lachmuth et al., 2025). As one of ZALF's central research infrastructures, the repository ensures institutionalised, long-term maintenance by its data management group, thereby securing continuity of the LTE-Map beyond its initial project-based development (funded primarily through BonaRes at the national level, and more recently through SoilWise at the European level). This stable framework allows the LTE-Map to serve as a hub for multiple networks, consolidating dispersed efforts into a common framework and enhancing their scientific visibility and reuse. For instance, metadata generated by projects such as EJP SOIL (Task 7.3) (Blanchy et al., 2024) and TUDI (<https://tudi-project.org/>), which might otherwise risk becoming inaccessible after project completion, are permanently hosted and remain accessible through the platform. Community engagement into the platform is necessary for its continuous updating and utility improvement. This is guaranteed through ongoing interaction with research networks at international level, e.g. substantially triggered by the Horizon Europe mission for soil health.

5. Limitations and future perspectives

While the LTE-Map provides a novel resource for documenting and discovering LTE metadata, some limitations must be acknowledged for future improvement. The current database is strongly biased toward Europe, which restricts its global representativeness and may skew research applications toward European pedo-climatic conditions. Recent collaborations with LTE initiatives (i.e., the TUDI Project) have supported expansion into eastern regions, particularly toward China, while metadata harvesting with international LTE networks (e.g., CIMMYT, LTAR) further offers important opportunities for broader global

integration and information exchange. Nevertheless, some regions, particularly Africa, still need substantial efforts due to limited data accessibility and the lack of publicly available metadata. In terms of FAIR alignment, the platform advances findability and accessibility but remains under development with respect to machine-actionable features. Notably, public APIs, persistent URIs for metadata schemas, and other automated tools (e.g., FAIR compliance checks) are still under development, which will be implemented in upcoming development phases to improve interoperability, reproducibility, and overall technical maturity.

At present, the LTE-Map is updated regularly but lacks a formal versioning system for recorded and published data and interim snapshots are instead archived in the BonaRes Repository (Dönmez et al., 2022a; Grosse et al., 2021). A formal versioning framework is planned with the future relaunch (in prep). We will then provide an open-source access to the codebase (currently maintained on GitHub up to 3 technical updates per year), thereby enhancing transparency and reproducibility. In 2026, the source code will be released on the map application as open source under the MIT license to ensure that the platform's codebase is publicly available and can be accessed by the research community for transparency, reproducibility, and community engagement. It will offer a range of new features, including a more intuitive user interface, improved search functions, and a new form for registering LTEs that will replace the current Fact Sheet.

The LTE-Map currently focuses on metadata, with a limited number of LTEs linking directly to datasets via persistent unique identifiers. This limits data reuse for many users, although ongoing efforts are recording persistent links from national and institutional repositories (e.g., CSIRO Data Access Portal, Rothamsted e-RA archive) to expand coverage and enhance dataset visibility. Evidence of platform impact is so far limited to reuse cases. While these demonstrate proof of concept, systematic user feedback and key performance indicators (e.g., active user, visitor count, frequency of data downloads, and citations of LTE-Map in scientific publications) are still lacking and will be focussed in future development phases. Establishing mechanisms for structured community feedback will also be crucial to guide platform improvements and

ensure that its functions align with the evolving needs of researchers and stakeholders.

6. Conclusion

The LTE-Map represents a novel scientific resource designed to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and interoperability of LTE data. By providing a standardized, geospatially structured platform, it facilitates global collaboration in agricultural research, enabling cross-site synthesis, data-driven insights, and informed decision-making. As an evolving tool, it is continuously presented at scientific conferences, fostering engagement with the research community and driving methodological advancements.

Despite our efforts, the majority of LTEs still remain geographically concentrated. Although most LTEs are listed as “ongoing” on the map, maintaining this status accurately is a challenge. It requires regular updates, and in some cases, trials may still be marked as ongoing simply because we lack the information needed to revise their status. To improve this process, looking ahead, further automation and digitalization efforts will enhance the map’s functionality. Key developments include streamlining data submission, integrating with repository upload tools, and implementing GeoNode conversion for improved spatial data management to further advance FAIR maturity, with special emphasis on machine-readability.

Besides its collection and management, data reuse is a cornerstone of modern agricultural research, enabling researchers to extract new insights from existing LTE datasets, conduct *meta*-analyses, and compare trends across diverse practices. Our LTE-Map plays a crucial role in [supporting data](#) reuse studies by providing structured metadata and facilitating access to diverse LTE datasets. The reuse case studies presented here are descriptive, illustrative, and exploratory, reflecting metadata coverage and illustrative reuse cases, rather than hypothesis-driven statistical testing. Moreover, while the platform primarily enables metadata reuse, it also includes a dedicated field for DOIs for each LTE, directing users to external repositories and platforms (e.g., BonaRes Repository, Swedish National Data Portal) where raw research datasets may be accessed. However, because generating LTE data is resource-intensive, especially due to the long-term maintenance required, some trial owners may be hesitant to share full datasets openly. These datasets are highly valuable, and collecting them in a standardized format could greatly accelerate research understanding of how ecosystems respond to various management practices.

Through joint efforts between the BonaRes team and the LTE community, our map has enabled the development of relevant LTE data reuse cases, demonstrating proof-of-concept for how long-term experimental metadata can support novel analyses. While not inferential in nature, these descriptive examples underline the map’s scientific utility and potential for future applications. By integrating metadata standardization, geospatial visualization, and repository linkages, the LTE-Map allows researchers to efficiently locate and combine LTE data for soil health assessments, sustainability modeling, and climate impact studies.

Moreover, by fostering interoperability between other LTE networks such as GLTEN, DRIVES, and LTEP-BIOCHAR, the LTE-Map strengthens cross-experiment comparisons, large-scale synthesis, and collaborative research. This structured approach to data discovery, accessibility, and reuse not only enhances the scientific value of existing LTE datasets but also accelerates evidence-based decision-making in agricultural sustainability and land management.

Particularly, in contrast to GLTEN, our map initially focused on Europe as comprehensively as possible before expanding globally. While many LTEs currently originate from Western countries, we recognize the importance of building a more globally representative database to further proceed in this direction. Some trials from African and Asian countries have already been included, and we hope to expand this effort in the coming years to ensure more inclusive insights for each continent.

Within the LTE-Map’s expansion to global, harvesting and harmonizing metadata with renowned LTE networks i.e. GLTEN could be an efficient next step to support networking within the LTE community. Overall, the LTE-Map has centralized metadata in a unified, geospatial platform, advanced FAIR principles through standardized formats and DOI linkages, and enabled data reuse via illustrative case studies. While it already improves metadata accessibility and reuse, particularly in Europe, future efforts, therefore, will be given to broaden its global coverage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cenk Dönmez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Xenia Specka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Carsten Hoffmann:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nikolai Svoboda:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Guillaume Blanchy:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Claire Chenu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Katharina Helming:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2026.111534>.

Data availability

The data and tools developed in this study are available at the following link: <https://lte.bonares.de>.

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